

Speculation of Quantum Bound State Thermodynamics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Feb. 15, 2022

Historically, thermodynamics was formulated for macroscopic systems followed by the development of statistical mechanics which provided microscopic formulations for quantities such as entropy. Entropy is traditionally linked to the \ln of the number states available or to the Shannon's form $-k \sum_i P(e_i) \ln(P(e_i))$ where $P(e_i)$ is the probability for the quantity e_i . In addition a variable T (linked to average kinetic energy) appears in both theories.

Later the Schrodinger equation was developed to describe bound electron states in an atom etc. These states were characterized by a math object $W(x)$ called the wavefunction and a set of discrete energy levels was calculated which matched data of emitted photons.

In a previous note (1) we argued that the average energy E_n for a quantum bound state plays the same role of characterizing equilibrium as T in classical thermodynamics/statistical mechanics. We further argued that E_n is linked to parameters in the system. For example, for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, E_n is linked to L as well as to n the energy level. One may change E_n by either changing n or L separately (or both). Holding L constant and changing n leads to a certain type of energy change. We argue this is similar to holding the volume of a gas constant and increasing T . Alternatively, one may leave n unchanged (a quantum adiabatic process) and change L i.e. a mechanical change or work. We argue that one may already consider the concept of the first law of thermodynamics at the quantum bound state level i.e. $dE = dQ - d\text{Work}$ where Work is linked to a change in a physical parameter, such as L the length of the box, whereas dQ is linked to energy changes not involving a physical parameter e.g. a change in n the energy level.

The Schrodinger equation yields solutions for $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ the wavefunction as well as E_n 's. We have argued in previous notes that $W(x)$ is part of a conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ and that E_n is constant at each point x just as T is constant at each x for classical statistical equilibrium (1). Thus a kind of statistical mechanics exists at the wavefunction level we argue. This statistical mechanics makes use of a free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ and weights $a(p)$, but does not contain the usual $P(x)$, $P(p)$ picture of the classical world. We have shown in (2) that one may obtain $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ from the conditional probability. The essential physics we argue, however, is at the level of the wavefunction together with its own unique statistical scenario of $\exp(ipx)$'s interacting with $\exp(ikx)$'s from $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ (see (1)).

Given that $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ exist for a quantum bound state, it may be convenient to use them in formulas because they are linked to a classical statistical picture. We argue that one may use $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ to construct an object S such that $T dS$ does not change when one changes L , the size of box with infinite potential walls. We argue that such an object follows from properties of the Schrodinger equation together with various assumptions. We arrive at $S = S_p + S_x$ where $S_p = -k \int dp a(p)a(p) \ln\{|a(p)a(p)|\}$ and $S_x = -k \int dx W(x)W(x) \ln(W(x)W(x))$ for a given energy level. We do not use arguments related to taking \ln of the number of states present or Shannon's entropy. Rather we look for a solution which does not depend on L and is additive. We note, however, that for both $W(x)W(x)$ and $a(p)a(p)$ the solution found is mathematically consistent with the entropy form found by considering independent probabilities.

This, however, applies to $P(x)$ and $P(p)$, but we argue that the physical situation is based on $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ as solutions of the Schrodinger equation. Nevertheless $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ are physical observables and not simply math constructs and so may think of them in a somewhat classical manner in terms of probability.

Thus we argue that thermodynamics is already present at the level of a quantum bound state and that one may obtain Shannon's entropy at this level using $P(x)$ and $P(p)$, but without considering the overall probability of independent probabilities as in information theory or numbers of states. Rather obtaining a function which is additive in S_p and S_x and eliminates L is the main consideration. We also argue that $S=S_p+S_x$ carries over into mixed quantum state wavefunctions even though it is usually ignored. Thus we try to argue that it is the bound quantum state which gives rise to the notion of thermodynamics and entropy.

Classical Entropy/Heat

In classical mechanics there exists the idea of work leading to changes in kinetic energy. If there is friction, however, kinetic energy may be lost to heat (and not regained). Thus there is more happening than just work. For example, one may heat a gas, but keep its volume constant. As a result, $dE = dQ - dW$ and one may define an energy related parameter T which describes equilibrium together with $dQ=TdS$ where S is a function called entropy. This characterization seems to be general and could just as well be used for a quantum bound state which depends on energy level n and external parameters such as L the length of 1-D box. The questions in such a case are: (a) What is T , the constant energy parameter in space? And (b) What is the form of S the entropy?

Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation

The time-independent Schrodinger equation is:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2 W_n(x)}{dx^2} + V(x)W_n(x) = E_n W_n(x) \quad ((1))$$

We have argued in previous notes that this is a statistical equation with E_n defining equilibrium i.e. it is an energy related constant for all x like T (1). $W(x) = \sum a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which is a momentum distribution using a priori $\exp(ipx)$ free particle probability linked objects (see (1)) with weights $a(p)$. The Schrodinger equation is not in a form containing the usual $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ values of classical probability. Furthermore $W(x)$ is the normalization constant of a conditional probability:

$$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) \quad ((2))$$

From $P(p/x)$ one may show that $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ (2) so quantum mechanics differs from classical physics which begins with notions of $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ and does not have a probability structure $\exp(ipx)$ associated with a free particle. The following question arises: Even if one may consider quantum mechanics to be a statistical theory, does it have any link to thermodynamics/statistical mechanics? If it does, one might expect that the quantum equations

should use $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ because these appear in classical theories. There is no $W(x)$ or $a(p)$ in such classical theories.

Particle in a Box with Infinite Potential Walls

Consider a particle in a 1-D box with infinite potential walls. In such a case, energy depends on n the energy level and L the size of the box through $E = b n^2 / L^2$ where b is a constant. Furthermore:

$$P(x) = W(x)W(x) = 1/L \sin(x/L)\sin(x/L) \text{ and } P(p) = a(p)a(p) = L f(Lp)f(Lp) \quad ((3))$$

For explicit forms see (3). At this point, E_n may be changed by holding n constant and altering L . This is a mechanical type of change similar to $-PdV$ in classical thermodynamics. A physical parameter is changed. Alternatively, one may hold L constant and change n , the energy level. If energy levels are very close (as they are for high n) then a change in energy level approximates the calculus dE_n . In such a case, mechanical work is not done, but energy changes so one may define the first law of thermodynamics:

$$dE_n = dQ - dW \text{ and } dQ = dS/T. \quad ((4))$$

We have already argued that E_n is constant throughout $[0, L]$ and so describes an equilibrium. The parameter T "called temperature" is introduced in order to have ((4)) mimic classical equations. The question arises: Can I use $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ which have classical probabilistic meaning (are real and positive) (unlike $P(p/x)$ or $W(x)$) and obtain a function S (entropy) such that a quantum adiabatic transformation leaves S unchanged? A quantum adiabatic transformation is linked to the thermodynamic form ((4)) because it involves changing a physical parameter e.g. L with n remaining constant. Given ((3)) any function:

$$F\{ P(x)P(p) \} \quad ((5))$$

Automatically eliminates L . One may note, however, that if the energy level n changes, then it is the set of $a(p)$'s which change, not $\exp(ipx)$. Overall this leads to a new $W_n(x)$, but it is the momentum weight $a(p)$ which is the driver. Furthermore in quantum mechanics it is stated that one may not measure p and x both with no uncertainty at the same time. These ideas seem to give rise to an additive entropy i.e.

$$S = S_p + S_x \quad ((6))$$

One may note that $P(x)$ contains $1/L$ and $P(p)$ L . If these are to disappear linearly, then a solution is:

$$\ln(1/L) + \ln(L) = 0 \quad ((7))$$

Thus, one may suggest:

$$S_x = -\int dx W W \ln(W W) \quad \text{and} \quad S_p = -\int dp a(p) a(p) \ln\{a(p) a(p)\}. \quad ((8))$$

These are in the form an average of both $\ln(W W)$ and $\ln(a(p) a(p))$.

As a result one may obtain an expression for entropy based on three main ideas:

- (A) $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ should appear. These exist both in quantum and classical physics.
- (B) S should not contain physical parameters such as L because these would suggest a change in L under a quantum adiabatic change which is not desired
- (C) $S = S_p + S_x$ i.e. is additive in terms of the functions of $P(p)$ and $P(x)$.

These three rules lead to a form for entropy for a quantum bound state. No ideas of the \ln of the number of available states or of information theory type independent probability products is needed to obtain ((8)). ((8)), however, does have the form of Shannon's entropy which exists in classical information theory. Is it possible that one may interpret it in the same way? The answer seems to be yes. Consider the usual information theory argument of $P(e_i)$ probabilities with each e_i event occurring $N P(e_i)$ times with N being very large. For $P(x)$ an e_i event involves finding the particle at x_i . Given the statistical nature of quantum mechanics and impulse hits, the theory does seem to point to such a picture if one uses $P(x)$. Thus:

$$\text{Probability} = \text{Product over } i \ P(x_i)^{N P(x_i)} = \text{product over } i \ \exp\{N P(x_i) \ln(P(x_i))\}$$

$$\exp(\text{Probability}) = \exp(\text{Sum over } i \ N P(x_i) \ln(P(x_i))) \quad \text{with} \quad S = - \text{Sum over } i \ P(x_i) \ln(P(x_i)) \quad ((9))$$

One may note that in classical statistical mechanics one often maximizes S by changing the form of $P(x_i)$ subject to certain constraint. In the quantum bound state this cannot be done because the form of $P(x)$ follows from $W(x)$ which in turn is a solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation. As a result, one must be careful when making arguments about the maximization of entropy in statistical situations. It is not maximized for a statistical quantum bound state (except for the ground state of an oscillator).

Mixed Energy Level Wavefunction

Above we have considered pure energy eigenstates, but a quantum wavefunction allows for mixed states i.e.:

$$W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } n \ b_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x) \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{Integrating yield} \quad \int dx W^*(x) W(x) = \text{Sum over } n \ b_n^* b_n$$

Thus one has probabilities $b_n^* b_n$ for the various energy levels. An entropy expression is often listed as (4)

$$S/(-k) = \text{Sum over } n \ b_n b_n \ln(b_n b_n) \quad ((11)) \quad \text{for } b_n \text{ real}$$

We have argued in (5) that one may instead include the effects of the entropy of the bound states. In fact we argue that the form of entropy follows from these. In such a case one has:

$$S/(-k) = \sum_n b_n \ln(b_n) + \sum_n b_n (S_{p,n} + S_{x,n}) \quad ((12))$$

If $S_{p,n} + S_{x,n}$ have small values and may be ignored then one may revert to ((10)). For example for high n values i.e. $n \rightarrow \infty$ $S_{p,n}$ approaches a constant i.e. does not depend on n . $S_{x,n}$ does not depend on n for any n value for a particle in a box with infinite walls.

Example of a Two Level Quantum System (Particle in a Box with Infinite Walls)

In (5) a two level quantum system is considered with:

$$b_1 b_2 = 1 / \{ 1 + \exp(-b_1 / (LLT)) \} \quad ((13)) \text{ where } b_1 \text{ is a constant}$$

For a quantum adiabatic transformation $b_1 b_2$ and $1 - b_1 b_2$ must remain unchanged so:

$T = \text{temperature}$ is proportional to $1/LL$.

If one considers a pure bound state (particle in a box with infinite walls) and changes n , then:

$$dE_n = b_2 (2n+1) / LL = dS/T \quad \text{but } S \text{ does not depend on } L, \text{ but } S_{p,n} \text{ so } T \text{ is proportional to } 1/LL.$$

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that the first law of thermodynamics seems to exist for a pure bound quantum state. We consider the example of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. In such a case $E_n = b n n / LL$ so one may change energy in two very different ways. One may change the physical parameter L (size of the box) which is a mechanical change or leave it constant and change n (e.g. absorb a photon). If one wishes to distinguish between these two, one may write the first law of thermodynamics i.e. $dE_n = dQ - PdL$. One may define $dQ/T = dS$ where T is a parameter and S a function called entropy. The main point of this note is to argue that the form of entropy already exists at the quantum bound state level. The Schrodinger equation may be solved for $W_n(x)$ and E_n , but $W_n(x)$ does not have a classical counterpart. In classical statistical physics one uses probabilities such as $P(x)$ and $P(p)$. These exist for a quantum bound state as well, namely $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a(p)a(p)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Thus it seems that one should write S entropy in terms of these so that it makes sense in classical terms. The two key points we argue are that S should not depend on L (so a quantum adiabatic transformation is L independent) and $S = S_x + S_p$ i.e. each should contribute in an additive manner. This leads to the form $S_x = - \int dx P(x) \ln(P(x))$ and $S_p = - \int dp P(p) \ln(P(p))$. No arguments regarding the counting of states are needed. One may note, however, that S_x and S_p both follow the form of Shannon's entropy and so may be

mathematically described in terms of information theory probability formulations, but we argue that the physical statistical description is contained in the time-independent Schrödinger equation. $P(x)$ and $P(p)$, however, are physical observables for quantum bound states and so are not merely math constructs.

References

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